
Drug-Drug Interaction between Amlodipine and Clarithromycin in Hypertension Rabbits

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ABSTRACT: This study is the first to examine the possibility of pharmacokinetic interaction in blood circulation using amlodipine and clarithromycin as representatives in hypertension rabbits and identify changes. The current study design required rabbits (n=6) for Pharmacokinetics. In group A, rabbits without treatment were used as control. In group B, were administration of a single dose of amlodipine (0.21mg/kg.BW) for 24 hours. Group C, were administered with a single dose of amlodipine (0.21 mg/kg/BW.) and clarithromycin (22 mg/kg/BW.) each 6 hr. for 24 hour. The blood samples were collected from (B and C) groups at time intervals of zero, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 96, 120, 144 hours and the drug concentrations were estimated using a spectrophotometer and estimated blood pressure using blood pressure cuff with Doppler ultrasound transducer. An increase in C max and AUC in group C (3.52 µg/ml and 130 µg/ml*h) respectively, indicates the improved bioavailability of amlodipine in the presence of clarithromycin compared with group B (2.03 µg/ml and 96.10 µg/ml*h) respectively. Furthermore, reduction in (CL) with an elevation of (Vd) in the presence of clarithromycin (54.94 L/kg/hr. and 4994 L/kg) in group C respectively, compared with group B (74.31 L/kg/hr and 3715 L/kg) respectively. We studied the influence of clarithromycin on the pharmacodynamics of amlodipine in hypertension rabbits. Interaction of amlodipine with multiple doses of clarithromycin produced a high reduction in blood pressure at 9 after administration and the blood pressure continues redaction. In conclusion, the combination of amlodipine with clarithromycin led to the enhancement of the bioavailability of amlodipine by inhibiting the CYP3A4 enzyme leading to producing a hypotension effect with peak plasma concentration effect in hypertension rabbits.

INTRODUCTION

Drug-drug interaction (DDIs) is a pharmacological or clinical reaction to the administration of a drug regimen different from that predictable from the known effects of the two agents when given separately (**Tornio et al ., 2012; Theodosios et al ., 2015; and May and Schindler, 2012**). In polypharmacy, it is important to find out the prevalence and rate of occurrence of drug interactions furthermore serious effects in hospitalized patients. As well, it is extra significant to detect and observed agents that are the majority to give harmful interactions (**Matheny et al ., 2001**). As per the survey, in about 3 to 5% of the patients taking a few drugs, drug-drug interaction can occur whereas it is nearly 20% in patients receiving a lot of drugs (**Janadei et al ., 2009 and Parameshappa et al ., 2010**). About (972 million) of the adult population worldwide has hypertension, according to the world health organization report (2010), and it's been growing within the last decade (**Oyedi et al., 2011**).

High blood pressure may affect the body's immune system and become more prone to infection. Infections in patients with hypertension necessary to be treated. antibiotic use is also quite common in hemodialysis patients, with a reported annual incidence of 32 % of such patients requiring hospitalization (**Chavers et al., 2007**). Therefore, antibiotic drugs such as clarithromycin and anti-hypertension medication such as amlodipine (CCBs) are required at the same time in these patients.

Thus, it's vital to study potential drug-drug interactions between antibiotic drugs and anti-hypertensive medication.

Amlodipine is a third-generation dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker that is widely used to treat high blood pressure and angina (**Johnson et al., 2019**). Absorption of amlodipine is well after oral administration and is extensively metabolized in the hepatic by Cytochrome P450 3A4/5 groups of enzymes and biotransformation primarily involves oxidation to its inactive form pyridine derivative M9, which M9 will affect by more oxidative deamination and transform into M10, O- demethylation to M1, and O-

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dealkylation to M4 (Zhu *et al.*, 2014). Macrolides (Clarithromycin, Erythromycin and Azithromycin) are widely prescribed antibiotics with more than sixty-six million prescriptions dispensed in (2008) in the United States alone (Wright *et al.*, 2011). Macrolides are the drugs of choice for patients with penicillin allergy. Though it is mostly well tolerated, they can give rise to drug interactions by numerous mechanisms, the most well-studied of these includes the cytochrome P450 enzymes inhibition which participates in the drug metabolism, for the most part, cytochrome P450 isoenzyme 3A4 (Fohner *et al.*, 2017).

This enzyme plays a vital role in the metabolism of several medications including calcium channel blockers like amlodipine (Kim *et al.*, 2006). These interactions are both dangerous and greatly underappreciated due to the elevation of amlodipine concentration leading to a decrease in blood pressure, several case reports described hospitalization with hypotension, cardiovascular (CV) toxicity, sudden cardiac death (SCD), soon after a CYP3A4 inhibitor was co-administration with amlodipine (Gandhi *et al.*, 2013). CYP3A4 is strongly inhibited by clarithromycin but not by azithromycin so when a macrolide antibiotic is obligatory, the interaction is simply avoided if azithromycin was given to patients who are previously receiving a calcium channel blocker (Wright *et al.*, 2011) To assess the selection, combination and possible drug-drug interactions of pharmacological agents used in the management of both infection and hypertension. It's necessary to check the doable effects of clarithromycin on some pharmacokinetics parameters of amlodipine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemical Reagents and Apparatus

Amlodipine oral tablet 5mg was purchased from Actavis Company (united kingdom). clarithromycin oral tablet 500 mg was purchased from Sandoz company (Germany).

Ethanol was purchased from BDH company England.

Pharmacokinetic Studies

Twenty-four rabbits (1.5- 2 Kg) were housed under controlled conditions. The animals were kept in individual cages, fed and watered ad libitum. They were submitted to experimentation after a 14-day adaptation period. A cannula was surgically inserted into the right of each study animal one day before blood sampling. In the multiple-dose interaction group (n=6), rabbits received an oral (0.21 mg/kg B.W.) single dose of amlodipine, which was followed by an oral dose of clarithromycin at (20 mg/kg B.W.) twice daily, for 24 hours. rabbits receiving only the same oral dose (0.21 mg/kg B.W.) of amlodipine were used as controls (n=6). The aqueous drug solutions were freshly prepared before dosing.

Blood was withdrawn via the cannula just before amlodipine administration (t=0) and at zero, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, 96, 120 and 144 hours after dosing. From these samples, plasma was immediately separated by centrifugation at 10,000 g for 5 min and was divided into two 100 mL aliquots. Plasma samples were stored at -20 C° until subsequent amlodipine analyses by spectrophotometer.

Preparation Of Diluent:

A combination of plasma rabbits with ethanol and water in the ratio of (1:1:8) was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 12000 rpm. After centrifugation, the resulting supernatant was collected and kept at (2-8 C°). This kept solvent is used for the study as a diluent.

Estimation Of Pharmacokinetic Parameters For Amlodipine

The maximum concentration in plasma and the time required to reach this concentration were obtained from the observed data for each rabbit. The area under the plasma concentration- versus time curve was calculated by using a linear trapezoidal estimation. The plasma concentration-time data of amlodipine were assessed by compartmental analysis. Least square regression analysis was employed directly on the data in both the distribution and terminal elimination phases for the estimation of apparent distribution (α) and elimination (β) rate constants, respectively.

Estimation Of Pharmacodynamics Parameter

Blood pressure levels were estimated using a blood pressure cuff with Doppler ultrasound transducer Method. The hypotension activity of amlodipine at any time 't' was calculated as the percentage reduction of blood pressure at that time with respect to initial blood pressure levels according to the Percentage reduction in blood pressure formula Percentage Reduction in Blood pressure at Time (Kim *et al.*, 2006). $T = a - b / a \times 100$ Where 'a' is initial blood pressure level and 'b' is blood pressure level at times.

RESULT

Linearity

The main objective for the investigation of an analytical technique I to prove that it is appropriate for its intended purpose and the parameters must be determined by the analyst's responsibility. Ethanol was needed as a solvent for Amlodipine. Amlodipine in plasma, ethanol and water (1:1:8) displayed extreme absorption in the UV spectrum at 343 nm. The Amlodipine curve was found as linear in the range of concentration of 5-40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The visual properties of the procedure and regression analysis of the calibration curve appear in Table (1).

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The linear curve was shown in the corresponding sample concentration range, and the regression value calibration curve (r^2) in solvent and plasma samples was 0.9997, and 0.9989, respectively. regression ratios display well intercept and slope values (Figures 1 and 2).

Accuracy

Accuracy of the technique was obtained by studying recovery at 3 dissimilar concentrations 50, 100, and 500 ng/ml of these predicted, by repeat analysis (n=6). A standard pharmaceutical solution was added to a pre-analyzed sample solution and the percentage of drug ingredient was calculated. The recovered percentages are shown in Table (2) the current method makes it easier to determine amlodipine in the form of pharmacological medication in a routine manner.

Precision

The intraday and interday precisions were determined by estimating the corresponding response three times on the same day and three different days over a period of a week for three different concentrations of amlodipine (10, 15, and 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) respectively. The result shows no significant change in response to amlodipine was observed after 24 hrs. Hence, the method is specific and robust for the estimation of Amlodipine (Table 3). Restoration of Amlodipine was found to be acceptable. Excipients used in the privacy study did not interact with the drug response in the analytical wavelength. Furthermore, no significant variation in Amlodipine response after 24 hours. Thus, a specific and powerful method for estimating amlodipine

Pharmacokinetic Data In Hypertension Rabbits

The plasma concentrations of amlodipine in hypertension rabbits before and after treatment with multiple doses of clarithromycin and plots of the time course of Mean $\pm$ SD Plasma concentrations of amlodipine following the oral route of administration vs. time were shown in tables (4) and figures (3,4,5) respectively.

Pharmacodynamics Parameters In Hypertension Rabbits

The percentage of blood pressure reduction by amlodipine in hypertension rabbits before and after treatment with multiple doses of clarithromycin was shown in tables (5). Hence the therapy with the combination was found not to be safe. The percentage of pressure reduction decreases gradually in proportion to the concentration of the drug until the drug is completely eliminated from the body.

Table 1. Calibration curve data for amlodipine in rabbits' plasma

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
5	0.15
10	0.29
15	0.46
20	0.62
25	0.75
30	0.92

Table 2. Results of Accuracy for Amlodipine

Sample No.	Quality control samples Amlodipine (ng/ml)	Recovered amount of Amlodipine (ng/ml)	Accuracy (%) Amlodipine
1	50	45	90%
2	100	90	98%
3	500	498	99.7%

Table 3. Intraday and interday precision of amlodipine in rabbits' plasma

	Intraday	Interday
Precision	20 μg	20 μg
	0.6102	0.6102
	0.6114	0.6105
	0.6111	0.6112
	0.6103	0.6101
	0.6112	0.6115
	0.611	0.610
Mean	0.6108 $\pm$ 0.0004	0.6105 $\pm$ 0.0005

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Table 4. Pharmacokinetic parameters of amlodipine after oral administration of amlodipine(0.2 mg/kg B.W)only, with multiple doses of clarithromycin (21mg/kg B.W) in induced hypertension rabbit

All values are expressed as mean $\pm$ SE (number of animals in each group=6).

Pharmacokinetic parameters	Amlodipine	A single dose of Amlodipine +clarithromycin (multi-dose)	LSD value
T _{1/2} Ka(hr)	2.42 $\pm$ 0.04 A	2.38 $\pm$ 0.01 A	0.20*
T _{1/2} ke (hr)	34.65 $\pm$ 0.13 A	63.0 $\pm$ 0.32 B	2.99*
C _{max} (μ g/ml)	2.03 $\pm$ 0.27 A	3.52 $\pm$ 0.09 C	0.13*
T _{max} (hr)	9.0 $\pm$ 0.22 A	9.0 $\pm$ 0.30 A	0.32*
Vd /F(L/Kg)	3715 $\pm$ 0.1 A	4994 $\pm$ 0.21 C	10.55*
CL/F(L/Kg/hr)	74.31 $\pm$ 0.05 A	54.94 $\pm$ 0.01 B	5.52*
AUC 0- ∞ (μ g/ml*h)	96.10 $\pm$ 1.02 A	130.0 $\pm$ 0.49 B	10.35*
Ka (1/hr)	0.28 $\pm$ 0.10 A	0.29 $\pm$ 0.05 A	0.09*
Ke(1/hr)	0.020 $\pm$ 0.02 A	0.0110 $\pm$ 0.01 B	0.001*
* (P $\leq$ 0.05).			

Table 5. The mean blood pressure of healthy and hypertensive rabbits before and during treatment with amlodipine alone and amlodipine with clarithromycin

Groups	Blood pressure mmHg					
	Mean Systolic blood pressure			Mean diastolic blood pressure		
	Normal Systolic	After 9 hr from treatment	After 24 hr from Treatment	Normal Diastolic	After 9 hr from treatment	After 24 hr From treatment
Group A (normal rabbits)	130 $\pm$ 0.3 A a	131 $\pm$ 0.4 A a	130 $\pm$ 0.5 A a	83 $\pm$ 0.2 A a	82 $\pm$ 0.1 A a	85 $\pm$ 0.6 A a
Group B (hypertension rabbits)	156 $\pm$ 0.6 B a	160 $\pm$ 0.5 B a	158 $\pm$ 0.3 B a	97 $\pm$ 0.3 B a	98 $\pm$ 0.2 B a	98 $\pm$ 0.4 B a
Group C (Induce hypertensive rabbits treated with Amlodipine alone)	159 $\pm$ 0.6 B a	145 $\pm$ 0.3 C a	135 $\pm$ 0.5 A b	98 $\pm$ 0.3 B a	87 $\pm$ 0.8 A a	85 $\pm$ 0.9 A b
Group D (Induce hypertensive rabbits treated with amlodipine $\pm$ clarithromycin)	160 $\pm$ 0.3 B a	135 $\pm$ 0.5 A b	110 $\pm$ 0.8 C c	98 $\pm$ 0.5 B a	85 $\pm$ 1.0 A b	75 $\pm$ 0.5 C b
LSD value	Rows =22.34		column =9.65	Rows = 10.82		column=6

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Figure (1): calibration curve of amlodipine in solvent

Figure (2): Calibration curve of amlodipine in plasma

Figure (3): Semi-log of ng/ml versus time (hr) after single oral administration of amlodipine (0.21 mg/kg B.W.)

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Figure (4): Semi-log of ng/ml versus time (hr) after single oral administration of amlodipine (0.2mg/kg B.W.) with oral administration of clarithromycin (20 mg/kg B.W.) twice daily.

DISCUSSION

These experiments confirm that the present method for the determination of amlodipine in rabbits' plasma samples was simple, sensitive, accurate and requires a relatively small volume of plasma (100 μ L). The calibration curve was linear in the concentration range of 5 and 40 ng/ml and hence the method is suitable for conducting pharmacokinetic studies (**Srinivasulu et al., 2015**).

The absorption of the drug was clearly evidenced by the observed absorption rate constant and absorption half-life. These findings indicated that amlodipine was completely absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract of rabbits. There was a significant rise in pharmacokinetic parameters like AUC and C max of amlodipine with multiple dose treatment of clarithromycin. These findings satisfy the result of (**Kim et al., 2018**) who stated that amlodipine is well absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract after oral administration and time to reach C max at 8-9 hours. The increase in AUC and C max indicates improved availability of amlodipine in the presence of clarithromycin. The increased bioavailability cannot be due to improved absorption, since the absorption rate and absorption half-life of amlodipine were not altered. There might not be interaction at the absorption level because both drugs are absorbed rapidly after oral administration, so the enhanced plasma amlodipine levels might be due to either inhibition of metabolism or alteration in the distribution of amlodipine in the presence of clarithromycin (**Gandhi et al., 2013**). The study indicates that the interaction observed was pharmacokinetic interaction. Clarithromycin is an inhibitor of CYP 450 3A4 (**Ohmori et al., 1993; Fohner et al., 2017**). Amlodipine is mainly metabolized by CYP 450 3A4 (**Zhu et al., 2014**). Hence the interaction may be occurring at the level of the metabolism also, clarithromycin acts as an inhibitor of the enzyme CYP 450 3A4 and delays the metabolism of amlodipine leading to its enhanced effect, Such an increase in exposure mirrored the significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in clearance and elimination rate constant with significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in elimination half-life. These results agree with (**Wright et al., 2011**). Furthermore, the volume of distribution was significantly increased ($p \leq 0.05$) in animals receiving oral clarithromycin.

The drug profile of amlodipine shows that it is a high protein tissue-bound drug i.e. about 95% was bound to tissue proteins. So the increase in the volume distribution when the amlodipine level increase might be responsible for the increase in its activity (**Ahsan and Khan 2017; Johnson et al., 2019**). Amlodipine in combination with clarithromycin produced hypotensive activity at 9hr in hypertension rabbits indicating the presence of interaction in pharmacokinetic parameters, since there was a change in absorption parameters of amlodipine like AUC, C max, clearance and also elimination parameters of amlodipine like $T_{1/2}$ and V_d in the presence of clarithromycin (**Gandhi et al., 2013; Kader et al., 2015; Chudow and Ferguson, 2018**). The amlodipine is metabolized by CYP 3A4 and clarithromycin inhibited the metabolism by an inhibitor of the same isoenzymes CYP3A4 there were significant changes in the absorption and elimination of amlodipine by clarithromycin were produced in the multiple-dose treatment (**Hayes, 2018**). Hence the therapy with the combination was found not to be safe. The percentage of blood pressure reduction decreases gradually in proportion to the concentration of the drug until the drug is completely eliminated from the body (**pinto et al., 2019**).

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